

IPBES invasive alien species assessment, data management report for Chapter 3. Section 3.3.3.3: Marine debris

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Description

Section 3.3.3.3 assesses the role of marine debris as a driver of biological invasions in Chapter 3 of IPBES thematic assessment of invasive alien species and their control. The experts conducted a systematic review to report on the existing knowledge on this driver. This systematic review consists in the main source of evidence for the section.

Process overview

Search 1:

Search 2:

Search 3:

Search 4:

Search 5:

Protocol

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** literature review
- **Search language(s):** English

- Search terms:

Search 1: Marine Plastic, filtered by marine plastic AND inv* Alien exotic

Search 2: urban* AND inva* OR alien OR exotic AND driver AND vector AND ecology AND marine

Search 3: Marine Plastic, filtered by microplastic AND invasive

Search 4: Marine litter AND Inv* AND vector AND Plastic AND dispersal

Search 5: Marine AND Inv* AND rafting AND Plastic AND dispersal

- Search engine: Web of Science

-Searched time period:

Search 1: 1900 to 2019

Search 2: 2014-2019

Search 3-5: 1900-2019

- Date:

Search 1: 10 October 2019

Search 2: 14 October 2019

Search 3: 15 October 2019

Search 4-5: 16 October 2019

- Overview of the search results and selection criteria:

Number of search result: 13 in total

Search 1: 1 (1 paper selected for review)

Search 2: 100 (1 paper selected for review)

Search 3: 10 (2 paper selected for review)

Search 4: 7 (6 papers selected for review)

Search 5: 15 (3 papers selected for review)

Selection criteria:

Articles that specified marine debris as a vector of introduction of IAS

Number of added papers (experts' knowledge and reviewers' recommendations):

9 papers were added following the external review comments.

- Step by step analysis (methodology, categories, etc.):

Number of papers reviewed: From the initial 133 papers found, the first scan included reviewing from the title and abstracts which ones were the most representative for the section, the ones that could include information of marine debris as a vector of introduction for IAS were fully read, and then 13 were selected to draft the section. Diversity on ecosystems and stages of the invasive process was prioritised. One more paper was added following the suggestion of a reviewer during the first external review.

Fields extracted:

- Publication title

- Year of publication

- Invasion stage [Uptake and transport; Introduction; Establishment; Spread]

- Biomes [Terrestrial; Freshwater; Marine]

- Taxon [Plant; Vertebrate; Invertebrate; Microbes]
- Type of study [Primary study; Review; Meta-analysis]
- Region [Europe and Central Asia; Asia-Pacific; Oceania; Americas; Africa]
- Unit of analysis [IPBES units of analysis]
- Cross-cutting theme [Scenarios and models; indigenous and local knowledge; Good quality of life]
- Comment (free text)

- **Files (code, review templates, etc.):**

[Chapter 3 literature review masterdatabase.xlsx](#)